

Relation between estimated number of eggs and observed number of hatching larvae.

Parameter estimates for multiple regression of number of larvae per egg mass on egg mass length and width.

Variable	Estimate	SE	t ^a
Length	19.88	2.03	9.80**
Width	16.44	5.00	3.29**

^a** = significant at the 1% level.

where y is the estimated number, was linear and highly significant ($R^2 = 0.875$, $df = 93$, $P < 0.01$) (see figure). The regression indicates that we slightly overestimated the number of eggs in small egg masses and slightly underestimated the number in large egg masses.

Other researchers have used multiple regression equations to predict the number of eggs per YSB egg mass from measurements of egg mass length and width. To evaluate this method, we measured the length and width of our 95 test egg masses before egg hatch and used these measurements as indepen-

dent variables in a multiple linear regression, with the number of hatching larvae as the dependent variable. The resulting equation, $y = 19.881 + 16.44w - 56.96$ (see table), explained only 61% of the variation in the number of hatching larvae (adjusted $R^2 = 0.61$).

Our results demonstrate that, at least in the hands of an experienced researcher, comparison with a reference collection can be a highly accurate technique for estimating the number of eggs in a YSB egg mass. The predictive power of an alternative method, the multiple regression technique, could perhaps be improved by adding egg mass thickness as an additional independent variable. Maximum thickness of the egg mass could be measured with a set of calipers, but the variable thickness of the egg mass is better taken into account by visual comparison with a reference collection. ■

Excel modeling environment: description and application to the ORYZA0 model

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ORYZA0 is a N-limited rice production model developed at AB-DLO (Wageningen) during the SARP project, in collaborative work with IRRI and NARS from rice-producing countries in Asia. It was originally written in FST (Fortran Simulation Translator), within DOS. We have recently produced an Excel worksheet version. Three approaches were considered: direct, custom, and advanced. The main difference is the user interface. The direct approach (Fig. 1) uses a simple method containing few computations. This approach is useful as a teaching tool. The custom approach permits many relations among parameters. Emphasis is on a clear presentation of model input-output listings. Main input and output data are put together

Leaf photosynthesis explanatory model			
Parameter description	Dimension	Formula	Value
Intensity of absorbed radiation (PAR)	$J m^{-2} s^{-1}$		150
Max. leaf photosynthesis (at saturated light)	$kg CO_2 ha^{-1} h^{-1}$		50
Initial light use efficiency	$kg CO_2 ha^{-1} h^{-1}$		0.40
Gross photosynthesis rate	$J m^{-2} s^{-1}$	$D12 = D7 * (1 - EXP(-D9 * D5 / D7))$	34.94

1. Example of a simple model written in Excel. The direct approach is used. The four columns allow easy understanding of data and calculations.

while computation and less important parameters are hidden. This approach allows users to concentrate on model output and to identify knowledge gaps through simulations. The advanced approach is similar to the custom approach but makes more use of macros, modules, and Visual Basic. Colors, borders, text styles, buttons, and windows are used to provide a user-friendly interface. The interface accompanies the user in a model shell, and it is easy to scroll, with clear input requests, fast simulation run, and improved output. The advanced ap-

proach enlarges the user range for direct application, for demonstration, and for teaching purposes.

An example of Excel modeling environment using the advanced approach (Fig. 2) is the model ORYZA0.xls. A model like ORYZA0 is composed of initial variables, input tables, and equations. All these can be easily converted in a spreadsheet. The Fortran model functions were translated into the spreadsheet where in most of the cases the statements are the same

State variables, rate variables, driving variables, tables, and subrou-

tines are located in different parts of the spreadsheet. Formulas and computations are not directly available to users. Help windows provide guidelines to correct data inserting and to output requirements. The model is shared into modules, each one located in a single sheet (crop sheet, weather sheet, soil sheet, fertilization sheet, graph, and output sheet).

We compared the FST model with the Excel model. No difference is found in the output values. Model speed is much higher with the Excel version because of translation, linking, and compiling constraints within the FST shell. The interface is greatly improved. Using the Windows editor, it is possible to partly or totally copy the model data in a word processor, in a database, or in a different spreadsheet. In addition data and graphs can be printed. ■

ORYZA 0

Press the buttons

About the MODEL

TIME & WEATHER		CROP DATA	SOIL DATA
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Click here to change
with 'X' the leaf nitrogen will be simulated, without the model will use the measured values

SIMULATION RUN

Main end simulation outputs	
14788	<i>kg d.m.tot.crop./ha</i>
7473.1	<i>kg d.m.YIELD/ha</i>

2. OryzaO Excel advanced approach. The "main window" of the model is presented. Moving the mouse and clicking on the buttons allow one to select one of seven windows of the model. The "simulation run" button runs the model and updates the main output.

Announcement

Fukui International Koshihikari Rice Prize

The Fukui International Koshihikari Rice Prize was established in 1997 to commemorate the 50th anniversary of the development of the rice cultivar Koshihikari in Fukui Prefecture, Japan. Koshihikari is renown throughout Japan for its outstanding grain quality. The development of Koshihikari is acknowledged as a typical case of a great contribution to domestic as well as international rice production achieved by a local agricultural experiment station. In 1995 during the 2nd

Asian Crop Science Conference held in Fukui, several representatives from the Crop Science Society of Asia and international agricultural research centers and national agricultural research systems proposed the establishment of an international prize to be awarded to rice researchers who have contributed to improving rice production through breeding, cultivation technology development, or other related fields. The Prize was established particularly to award rice researchers working in universities and international, national, and local agricultural research stations.

The Prize will be given to three outstanding researchers. The laureates, who will be invited to an awards ceremony to make a presentation on their achievements, will be awarded 300,000 Japanese yen each. The deadline for the nominations is 31 Dec 1997. Nomination forms are available from the Secretariat for the Fukui International Koshihikari Rice Prize, Fukui Agricultural Experiment Station, 52-21 Ryo-machi, Fukui City, Japan; fax: 81-776-54-5106. ■